

Prediction versus Truth Plots for “Function Approximation for High-Energy Physics: Comparing Machine Learning and Interpolation Methods”

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Prediction versus Truth Plots

In addition to boxplots that quantitatively summarize the performance of each approximant, it is useful to look at prediction versus truth plots which can reveal the scales at which the approximants are performing better or worse. The following plots show the approximant predictions versus the true values of the test functions in various dimensions on 50,000 points. These plots provide further evidence for the superiority of MLP over the other approximants.

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Prediction versus truth for the polynomial function

Figure 1: Prediction versus truth plots for the polynomial function in 3 dimensions.

Prediction versus truth for the periodic function

Figure 2: Prediction versus truth plots for the periodic function in 3 dimensions.

Prediction versus truth for the Camel function

Figure 3: Prediction versus truth plots for the Camel function in 3 dimensions.

Prediction versus truth for the D3 function

Figure 4: Prediction versus truth plots for the D3 function in 3 dimensions.

Prediction versus truth for the polynomial function

Figure 5: Prediction versus truth plots for the polynomial function in 6 dimensions.

Prediction versus truth for the periodic function

Figure 6: Prediction versus truth plots for the periodic function in 6 dimensions.

Prediction versus truth for the Camel function

Figure 7: Prediction versus truth plots for the Camel function in 6 dimensions.

Prediction versus truth for the D6 function

Figure 8: Prediction versus truth plots for the D6 function in 6 dimensions.

Prediction versus truth for the polynomial function

Figure 9: Prediction versus truth plots for the polynomial function in 9 dimensions.

Prediction versus truth for the periodic function

Figure 10: Prediction versus truth plots for the periodic function in 9 dimensions.

Prediction versus truth for the Camel function

Figure 11: Prediction versus truth plots for the Camel function in 9 dimensions.

Prediction versus truth for the D9 function

Figure 12: Prediction versus truth plots for the D9 function in 9 dimensions.

Figure 13: Prediction versus truth plots for the Camel function in 9 dimensions.

Figure 14: Prediction versus truth plots for the M function in 5 dimensions.